

Employee-Learning Orientation and Innovation Performance: Assessing the Mediating Role of Organizational Learning and the Moderating Role of Transformational Leadership

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Abstract

This paper examines the role played by the employee-learning orientation (ELO) in producing organizational learning (OL) and innovation performance (IP). It also aims at assessing the mediating effect of the organizational learning on the employee-learning orientation- innovation performance link. In addition, it aims at evaluating the moderating role played by the transactional leadership (TL): on one hand, on the relationship between the ELO and the OL; on the other hand, on the indirect effect of the ELO on the IP through OL. This article explores these relationships using structural equations modeling with partial least squares technique with data set from the medical biotechnology industry in France. The results support all but one of the hypotheses and have important implications for both academics and practitioners, in the field of organizational learning, strategic leadership and innovation performance.

Key words: employee learning orientation, innovation performance, organizational learning, transactional leadership.

JEL Classification: M11; M12 ; O32; L25; C39

1. Introduction

The literature suggests that innovative firms are effective learning organizations where human capital is developed and where firms learn to enhance their performance. According to Calantone et al (2002), innovation and performance are closely related to organizational learning. The starting point and the foundation of the organizational learning is the individual learning (Marsick and Watkins, 2003), the personal mastery (Senge, 1990), the personnel development (Belet, 2003) and, the employee-learning orientation (Gong et al, 2009). In this line, Senge(1990) notes that the dynamics of mastery and organizational learning are inseparable. Some studies suggest that individual learning relates directly to innovation performance (Garcia-Morales et al, 2012). Other studies demonstrate an indirect effect of the individual learning on the innovation performance through the organizational learning (Hsu and Fang, 2009). The contingencies of employee-learning orientation and performance outcomes have, surprisingly, received little research attention. Among these contingencies, Marsick and Watkins (2003) highlighted the key role played by the strategic leadership. Indeed, they demonstrated that the people level of the learning organization influences system variables, which in turn positively influence the firm performance but only when moderated by strategic leadership for learning. Marsick and Watkins (2003, p.142) note: "This research provides more evidence that workplace learning programs not supported by leaders who understand the strategic role of learning will have less effect on the very reasons why corporations invest in HRD in the first place - to impact current and future financial performance".

The conceptual literature points out implicit assumption that strategic leadership, namely the transformational one, is crucial to the organizational learning (Vera and Crossan, 2004). However, empirical studies, especially those quantitative specifying the conditions under which the employee-learning

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orientation -organizational learning link is optimized through transformational leadership are very scarce (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007).

Employee-learning orientation (ELO), organizational learning (OL), transformational leadership (TL) and innovation performance (IP) relate to each other (Montes et al, 2005). However, research that studies the inter relationships between these concepts simultaneously remains scarce. Previous studies usually focus on the impact of the organizational learning orientation on the innovation and on the performance. Even when introducing employee-learning orientation, this is done in a more global context, considering that ELO as a variable of the learning organization and thus not taking into account its precise and individualized effect on organizational learning and innovation performance. Thus, previous research provides an unclear explanation of the role played by the ELO in the improvement of the OL and the IP. This study attempts to address the weaknesses of the preceding literature by empirically assessing the relationships between employee-learning orientation, organizational learning, transformational leadership and innovation performance together in a single model. Especially, our study seeks to highlight the necessity to investigate how ELO influences innovation performance through organizational learning; and how this link (ELO-OL-IP) is influenced by transformational leadership. The article starts with a review of the literature on these topics and a set of testable hypotheses is proposed. The implemented methodological frame is then introduced. The next section presents the main results of the survey. Following a discussion of the results, implications, limitations and proposals for future research are presented.

2. The Framework and Hypotheses

• Employee-Learning Orientation and Organizational Learning

Gong et al, (2009) defined an employee-learning orientation as an internal mind-set that stimulates employees to develop their competencies. Such employees are on the lookout for challenges that provide them with continuous learning opportunities (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007). When employees enhance their learning capacity, they can improve the organizational capacity to learn. This is conditioned by an organizational climate receptive to the individual learning, putting in place suitable mechanisms to facilitate, support and reward the knowledge generation and its sharing and exploitation (Marsick and Watkins, 2003). According to the 4Is model of organizational learning, developed by Crossan et al (1999), it is argued that individual learning is a crucial step toward the organizational learning process. Vera and Crossan (2004, p. 225) defined the learning process involved in the 4I framework: "Intuiting is a subconscious process that occurs at the level of the individual. It is the start of learning and must happen in a single mind. Interpreting then notices the conscious elements of this individual learning and shares it at the group level. Integrating follows to change collective understanding at the group level and bridges to the level of the whole organization. Finally, institutionalizing incorporates that learning across the organization by imbedding it in its systems, structures, routines, and practices". In summary, employee-learning orientation captures the processes of intuiting and interpreting. Individuals facilitate organizational knowledge exploitation through sharing it with others. They also promote organizational knowledge exploration through generating new insights. Hsu and Fang (2009) assert that organizational learning depends on the sharing and integration of extant knowledge, and ideas explored by organizational members. The better the employee learning orientation, the more knowledge produced to enhance organizational learning capability. Based on the discussion above, this study offers the following hypothesis:

H1: Employee-learning orientation will have a positive effect on organizational learning capability.

• Employee-Learning Orientation, Organizational Learning and Innovation Performance

Prior studies asserted that the creation of intelligent organizations based on innovation performance is conditioned by the exploitation and the development of the human capital and by the use of the individual learning potential (Nonaka, 1997). Hult et al, (2004) stated that if a firm is to be innovative, it must foster a management that reflects a clear learning orientation. Specifically, an employee-learning orientation is conducive to the acquisition of knowledge and skills, which enhance the creativity and the innovation

effectiveness. In this regard, Garcia-Morales et al (2007, p.548) noted: “The most innovative firms are effective learning systems where human resources are developed and where firms learn to maintain today’s competitive advantages while aggressively preparing for tomorrow”. Empirically, Plott (1998, cited by Bontis et al, 2002) showed that firms that invest more heavily on employee-learning orientation are more successful and better rated by the stock market exchange. As individual learning is supposed to improve the human capital of the firm, we can consider that a firm with a better employee quality will have higher innovation performance because its workforce can bring skills and capabilities into full play (Hsu and Fang, 2009).

Some authors (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007) pointed out that the effect of the employee-learning orientation on innovation performance is of an indirect nature. Indeed, they asserted that employee-learning orientation provides the framework for the generation of the organizational learning, which in turn influences the innovation performance. In this spirit, Hsu and Fang (2009) showed that the organizational learning capability played a mediating role between the human capital of a firm and the product innovation performance. The foregoing demonstrates that organizational learning is an antecedent of the innovation performance and that employee-learning orientation is an antecedent of the organizational learning. This is in line with the thoughts of Park and Kim (2006) seeing that the achieved innovation performance of a firm is the reflection of the effectiveness and efficiency of its learning processes. Based on these discussions, this study predicts the following hypotheses:

H2: Employee-learning orientation will have a positive and direct effect on innovation performance.

H3: Employee-learning orientation will have a positive and indirect effect on innovation performance through organizational learning capability.

• **The Effect of the Transformational Leadership**

Two distinctions are made by Hambrick and Pettigrew (2001, cited by Vera and Crossan, 2004) with regard to the terms leadership and strategic leadership. First, leadership studies leaders at any organizational level, whereas strategic leadership studies leaders at the top of the organization. Second, leadership theory refers to the relationship between leaders and followers, whereas strategic leadership theory refers to executive work, not only as a relational activity, but also as a strategic and a symbolic activity (Vera and Crossan, 2004). In this study, we adopt the strategic leadership theory; thus, we focus on how the leaders at the top of the firm influence the organizational learning process. Strategic leadership behaviors are usually classified into transformational and transactional styles (Peltokorpi and Hasu, 2014). In this study, we focus on transformational leadership (TL) because it is shown to enhance performance and innovativeness. TL refers to the ability of the leader to lead his subordinates transcend their personal interests and transform their beliefs, needs and values on behalf of a collective vision. While previous literature has highlighted the key role played by the transformational leadership in supporting the organizational learning (Montes et al, 2006), most of this work is prescriptive in nature and says little about the specific contribution of this leadership style with regard to the employee-learning orientation - organizational learning link. This study breaks new ground by examining how the relationship between employee-learning orientation and organizational learning is contingent with transformational leadership.

Vera and Crossan (2004) and Garcia-Morales et al, (2012) indicate that the most adopted definition of transformational leadership is that proposed by Bass (1999). This latter considers that transformational leadership is the interaction result of four components: the charismatic influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

Given that transformational leaders tend to be charismatic, they are natural role models whom employees are likely to identify with, emulate, and learn from (Vera and Crossan, 2004). Furthermore, through inspirational motivation, leaders behave in motivating ways and articulate an exciting vision that inspires followers by implanting challenge of high expectation in their work. In addition, transformational leaders encourage intellectual stimulation by promoting employees’ efforts to be creative by thinking about old problems in new ways, questioning assumptions and taking risks. Therefore, employees can generate

double-loop learning and be more innovative. Through individualized consideration, transformational leaders pay attention to each individual's need for learning by acting as a mentor and coach. In addition, by individualized consideration, leaders show empathy, recognition and encouragement for employees, which should support overcome internal skepticism and the fear of challenging the status quo, leading to higher creativity, learning and, innovation.

Conceptual publications suggest that transformational leadership strengthens the relation between individual learning, organizational and firm performance outcomes (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007). Some researchers believe that organizational learning will flourish when a supervisor provides transformational leadership (Belet, 2003) and when an employee-learning orientation is established within a firm (Marsick and Watkins, 2003). Based on these arguments, we expect that the employee-learning orientation will produce higher organizational learning when transformational leadership is high rather than low. This study predicts the following hypotheses:

H4: Transformational leadership moderates the relationship between employee-learning orientation and organizational learning.

H5: The indirect effect of employee-learning orientation on innovation performance via organizational learning will be stronger when transformational leadership is high rather than low.

The conceptual model (except H4) of this study is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Model

3. Methodology

- **Measures**

The questionnaire consisted of 20 items, split into four parts that measure employee-learning orientation, transformational leadership, organizational learning and innovation performance. The measurements of employee-learning orientation and transformational leadership were extracted from the Dimensions of Learning Organization Questionnaire (DLOQ), originally developed by Watkins and Marsick (2003). The results of studies done to test the validity and reliability of the DLOQ have confirmed the internal consistency of each item's reliability and reliable factor structure of its dimensions (Song et al. 2009). These two dimensions were measured by 7 and 6 items respectively, on a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Organizational learning measurement was measured with two items, based on Pedon and Schmidt's (2003) instrument. The items in this instrument took the form of a five-point Likert scale ranging from "not achieved result" to "perfectly achieved result". Innovation performance measurement, inspired from the

studies of Alegre et al (2006) and Hsu and Fang (2009) was measured with five items. We ask respondents to state the performance of their product innovation on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “not achieved result” to “perfectly achieved result”.

- **Sample and Data Collection**

This study concentrates on the medical biotechnology (MB) industry in France. Several factors led to choosing this industry as the sample. First, the medical biotechnology industry is an intellectually capital-intensive industry where human capital and organizational learning play a crucial role. Second, MB firms face a tough environment and must continually produce product innovation. Third, many scholars have used this industry as a research sample in the organizational learning, innovation and performance field (Alegre and Chiva, 2008). Finally, MB industry in France accounts for nearly 10% of worldwide turnover with 14 Mds€, and ranks fourth in the world, making it a suitable ground to research (LEEM, 2011).

To collect data, this study uses a survey method. The sample pool consists of 322 MB firms listed in the national database of biotechnology (<http://www.biotechnologiefrance.org/>). The survey was conducted in two waves from February to April. Three weeks after the first emailing of questionnaires, we sent a reminder email to non-respondents and a second questionnaire. The number of valid questionnaires obtained was 76, yielding a response rate of 23.6%. We compared respondent and non-respondent firms with regard to general characteristics and model variables. These comparisons did not show significant differences, suggesting no response bias.

- **Analytical Procedures**

To test the hypotheses, we use structural equation modelling (SEM) method. The estimation technique we used under SEM is the Partial Least Square (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS package version 2.0.M3. This technique was chosen as the analytical procedure because of these reasons: First, it is in accordance with our objective, which focuses on explaining the variance of key target constructs (IP) by explanatory construct (ELO and OL). Second, it is flexible in sample size and is not rigid with non-normal distributed data. Third, it is efficient in modelling and simultaneously assessing both measurement and structural complex models with mediating and moderating variables (Chin, 2008).

4. Results

The estimation of a model under PLS requires two steps: the assessment of the measurement model (outer model) and the evaluation of the structural model (inner model).

- **Evaluation of the Measurement Model**

To assess the validity and the reliability of the variables, we carried out exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirming their dimensionality. Table 1 show the measurement analysis results, including item loadings, composite reliabilities (CR), average variances extracted (AVE), and Cronbach's alpha. Items under the threshold of 0.6 were dropped as suggested by Hair et al (2013) and Raza and Hanif (2013). The rest of item loadings, ranging from 0.620 to 0.905, were significant ($t > 1.96$).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics, Reliability, and Convergent Validity

Variable	Item	Mean	SD	Loading	α	CR	AVE
Employee Learning Orientation	ELO1*	4,158	0,784	-	0.721	0.824	0.542
	ELO2*	3,645	0,778	-			
	ELO3*	4,039	0,701	-			
	ELO4	3,408	0,969	0.772**			
	ELO5	3,684	0,852	0.690**			
	ELO6	3,671	0,806	0.845**			
	ELO7	3,171	0,929	0.619**			
Organizational learning	OL1	4,039	0,701	0.907**	0.766	0.895	0.810
	OL2	3,618	0,923	0.894**			
Innovation performance	IP1	2,947	1,210	0.755**	0.848	0.892	0.626
	IP2	3,171	1,012	0.897**			
	IP3	3,158	1,020	0.840**			
	IP4	3,026	0,979	0.811**			
	IP5	3,566	1,075	0.626**			
Transactional leadership	TL1	4,105	0,759	0.658**	0.832	0.877	0.543
	TL2	4,118	0,765	0.742**			
	TL3	3,737	0,839	0.773**			
	TL4	3,789	0,899	0.717**			
	TL5	3,750	0,881	0.712**			
	TL6	4,250	0,802	0.810**			

Note.* dropped item ; ** p < 0.05

For the four variables, AVE values, ranging from 0.547 to 0.810, are above the threshold of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2013), indicating convergent validity. The composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach’s alpha (α) values exceeded the acceptable cut off point of 0.7, confirming the good reliability of the variables.

The discriminant validity was evaluated using Fornell and Larcker criterion (table 2), which requests that the square root of each variable’s AVE (boldface diagonal elements in table 2) should be larger than the level of correlations involving the variable. All variables satisfy this condition.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

	ELO	OL	IP	TL
ELO	0.736			
OL	0.441	0.900		
IP	0.469	0.394	0.791	
TL	0.443	0.465	0.094	0.737

These results lend sufficient confidence that the measurement model fits the data well and has the adequate validity to take the next step: the evaluation of the structural model.

• **Evaluation of the Structural Model**

The approach suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986) was adopted to test the mediation model (H1, H2 and H3). Based on this approach, the mediation model was examined via a regression analysis through three steps. First, innovation performance is the dependent variable, and employee-learning orientation is the independent variable. Second, organizational learning is the dependent variable, and employee-learning

orientation is the independent variable. Third, organizational learning adds to employee-learning orientation and regresses with innovation performance. These relations are examined by assessing the direction, strength and level of significance of the path coefficients, using a bootstrap re sampling method with 1000 re-samples (Chin, 2008).The results (Table 3), indicated that the employee-learning orientation is directly and positively related with organizational learning ($\beta=0.464$; $t=3.687$), confirming H1.

Table 3: The Results of the Mediated Model (H1, H2 and, H3)

Step	Coefficient	Regression	β	T	R ²	Q ²
1	c	ELO>>>IP	0.471	6.260	22.1%	12.6%
2	a	ELO>>>OL	0.464	3.687	21.6%	13.8%
3		(ELO+OL)>>>IP				
3-1	c'	ELO>>>PIP	0.346	3.684	25%	13.7%
3-2	b	OL>>>PIP	0.237	2.246		

Employee-learning orientation also directly and significantly influences innovation performance with a path coefficient of 0.471 ($t=6.260$), and therefore, H2 is supported. To test H3, we performed a multiple regression on the independent variables. As shown in table 3, organizational learning is positively related to the innovation performance and the impact of the employee-learning orientation on the innovation performance remained positive but became smaller ($\beta=0.346$; $t=3.684$). To check the significance of this reduction, the Sobel test was used (Sobel, 1982). The results of this test ($z=4.497$, $p=0.000$) confirm that organizational learning exerts a mediating effect. However, the effect of the employee-learning orientation on innovation performance, controlling for organizational learning, had nonzero coefficients. Thus, the mediation is of a partial nature and H3 is supported. We note that all R² values exceeded the cutoff level of 19%, indicating a good predictive accuracy of our model (Chin, 2008).In addition, all Q² values were greater than zero and confirm, therefore, that our model had satisfactory predictive relevance (Wilson, 2010).

With respect to H1, we considered the contingent effect of transformational leadership on ELO-LO link. H4 was examined using the procedure outlined by Hense lerand Fassot (2010). According to this approach, firstly, the dependent variable is regressed on the independent variable and on the moderator (main effects model). Secondly, the regression effect of the dependent variable on the product term of the independent variable and the moderator is introduced (interaction effects model).Transactional leadership had a direct and positive effect on the organizational learning under the main effects model. Then, as shown in table 4 (second regression), in the interaction effects model, the path coefficient from the product term on the organizational learning was positive and significant ($\beta=0.341$; $t=2.530$), therefore H4 was supported.

Table 4: The Results of the Moderated Mediation Model (H4 and H5)

Predictors	Regression 1 (criterion : IP)		Regression 2 (criterion : OL)		Regression 3 (criterion : IP)	
	β	t	B	t	β	t
	Independent variable : ELO	0.452	3.346*	0.305	2.411*	0.388
Moderator : TL	-0.136	0.758 ^{ns}	0.245	2.349*	-0.171	1.082 ^{ns}
Product term : ELO*TL	-0.308	0.943 ^{ns}	0.341	2.530*	-0.102	0.901 ^{ns}
Mediator : OL	-	-	-	-	0.223	2.118*
Product term : OL*TL	-	-	-	-	0.014	0.086 ^{ns}
R ²	31.2%		33.6%		34.1%	
Q ²	16.1%		21.9%		16.9%	

Note.* $p<0.05$; ns : not significant

The test of H5 refers to moderated mediation. We used the procedure suggested by Muller et al. (2005) which consists in a three multiple regression analysis. First, the dependent variable (IP) is regressed on the independent variable (ELO), the moderator (TL) and the product-term: ELO*TL. Second, the mediator (OL) is regressed on the independent variable, the moderator, and the product-term: ELO*TL. Third, the dependent variable is regressed on the independent variable, the moderator, the product-term: ELO*TL, the mediator and the product-term: OL*TL.

The results of the moderated mediation model are presented in Table 4. The first regression analysis showed the positive effect induced by the employee-learning orientation ($\beta=0.452$; $t=3.346$), but the transactional leadership and the product term (ELO*TL) did not reach statistical significance. The ELO impact on innovation performance did not depend on transactional leadership and this is a condition for a moderated mediation to occur. The second regression showed a significant effect of the employee-learning orientation on the mediator (OL) and, a significant relationship between the innovation performance and the ELO*TL product term. The last regression displayed significant effects of the ELO and the mediator (OL) on the innovation performance, but neither the ELO*TL product term nor the TL*OL were significant. The second regression result demonstrated that the relationship between employee-learning orientation and organizational learning is moderated by the transactional leadership as said above (H4). However, the third regression result showed that the transactional leadership does not moderate the OL-IP link as the product term TL*OL was not significant. Likewise, the transactional leadership does not moderate the ELO-IP link since the product term ELO-TL was not significant. This means that the mediated model is not moderated, suggesting that H5 is rejected.

5. Discussion

This study has shown that the employee-learning orientation as developed by Marsick and Watkins (2003) is somehow an appropriate measurement for the MB firms in France. Suppression of some ELO items reflects the cultural differences between the Anglo-Saxon and the Francophone contexts. Transactional leadership instrument as proposed by Marsick and Watkins (2003) is perfectly appropriate for the MB industry in France. The validation of the ELO and TL scales is in line with previous studies done in a variety of contexts (Song et al, 2009) confirming the robustness of these measurements and lending further generalizability to them. In addition, the OL and IP measurements are well validated in our context study. This implies that MB firms achieved high levels of simple and double loop learning as well as good new product market performance. This shows that the biotechnology sector is expanding and thus reflecting its increased importance in the national economy.

The confirmation of H1 and H2 is consistent with theoretical developments of several authors (Garcia-Morales, 2007; Hsu and Fang, 2009) seeing that the ELO is a crucial practice for the development of organizational learning and innovation performance. The finding that ELO positively relates to the OL is in line with Hsu and Fang study (2009). These authors confirmed that good quality employees committed to learning, efficiently produce knowledge and enhance absorptive capacity of the firm. As a result, an ELO will generate better skilled employees, leading to improved organizational learning capability. Otherwise, individuals committed to continuous personal development with a high degree of an ELO will have a high level of systems thinking, qualities that facilitate organizational learning (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007). In addition, confirming the positive effect of the ELO on the IP is consistent with Bontis et al study (2002). Thus, the more ELO flourishes, the better the firm's chances of becoming innovative will be, since individual learning fosters the different conditions driving innovation, such as motivation, training, sharing knowledge, and systems thinking. Indeed, greater emphasis on ELO nurtures the firm with new insights, improves the capacity to appreciate new ideas and boosts creativity and the ability to explore and exploit new opportunities.

With regard to H3, comparing the model without mediating effect to the mediated model, the direct effect of ELO on innovation performance decreases when including organizational learning as a mediating variable ($\beta=0.47$ decreases to $\beta=0.37$). Moreover, the ELO effect on OL and OL effect on innovation

performance remain significant showing that ELO affects IP through OL. This result confirming that the LO mediates the relationship between the ELO and the IP is consistent with previous literature. Indeed, Real et al, (2012) showed that the OL mediates the relationship between the learning organization and perceived business performance. Likewise, Hsu and Fang (2009) showed that the relationship between the human capital and product innovation performance was mediated by the OL capability. In our study, the percentage of the mediating effect ($me=100*ab/c$) has reached 23% of the total effect. Thus, the LO explains 23% of the ELO effect on the innovation performance. We have demonstrated that the mediation through the LO was of partial type. In other words, other mediating factors should be involved to explain the effect of the ELO on IP.

The present study supports the moderating effect of transformational leadership (H4) between employee-learning orientation and organizational learning. Specifically, it was found that an employee-learning orientation of a MB firm, when supported by a transactional leadership, is likely to generate a higher organizational learning level. Indeed, comparing the non-moderated model (H2) to the moderated model (H4), the explained variance (R^2) of the LO increases from 21.6% to 33.6%, showing the importance of transformational leadership. These findings are in line with the results from previous studies which have supported the moderating effect of the TL (Marsick and Watkins, 2003; Garcia-Morales et al, 2007). According to Vera and Crossan (2004), it is imperative to recognize that investments in an ELO may be wasted if the role of the TL, in stimulating and motivating the transfer and the sharing of the built stocks of individual learning to group and organizational levels, is not ensured.

The moderated mediation model was not supported in this study. Thus, the indirect effect of the ELO on the IP through the OL is not dependent on the level of the TL. The linkage is novel because there were not any previous studies taking into account such relationships within the same model. As shown by the second regression under the moderated mediation model, the TL has demonstrated its importance mainly by a positive direct effect on the OL and by a positively moderated effect on the same variable. This implies the necessity to foster transformational leadership in order to stimulate directly and indirectly, organizational learning, through its interaction with the ELO.

6. Conclusions

In this study, a framework for studying employee learning orientation, organizational learning, transactional leadership, and innovation performance was developed. The model was tested using data collected from MB firms in France. The findings support all but one of the hypotheses and have important implications in the field of organizational learning, strategic leadership and innovation performance.

• Implications

In summary, this research contributes to the literature, first, by Examining, in a same model, the relationships between the aforementioned variables. Second, it provides empirical support that employee-learning orientation improves directly and indirectly, through organizational learning, innovation performance. Indeed, ELO is an antecedent of the OL, which in turn relates positively to the IP. Hence, the importance for academics to take the mediating effect of the OL into account when examining the ELO-IP link. Third, it contributes to the literature by assessing the likely moderating effect of the transactional leadership on the relationship between ELO and OL. The findings contribute to confirm that the relation between ELO and OL is contingent upon TL. Fourth, although this study has not confirmed H5, it highlights the importance of taking into account the contingencies related to organizational phenomena through mobilizing intermediate variables (moderators and mediators) to better explain and reflect studied realities.

The main methodological contribution of the current research is that we have demonstrated, through the appropriateness of Partial Least Square in the estimation of a complex model, containing moderator and mediator variables, with a small sample, the flexibility of this technique. This pleads for a more frequent use of it in the estimation of structural equation models in management science.

This work also provides implications for practitioners. First, although practitioners recognize the idea that learning orientation influences innovation performance, how to go about this phenomenon stayed unclear. The present study suggests that ELO relates positively, directly and indirectly through organizational learning, to innovation performance. Therefore, a firm hoping to enhance its innovation performance should improve its organizational learning processes. Thus, by recognizing that the greatest part of the value accumulated in innovation arises from human intelligence, that is, from the individual learning of the employees, HR managers should consider ELO as the firm's most valuable resource, "a resource for which large firms and SMEs must take responsibility and whose professional development it must promote" (Garcia-Morales et al, 2007, p. 560). In addition, HR managers should recruit employees not only with suitable qualifications, but also with great willingness to become better through learning. Next, these employees should be supported to participate in firm training courses and to commit to long-term employee development programs. Employees should be encouraged to help each other learn, to explore new knowledge, and to openly discuss mistakes in order to learn from them. Second, because the results suggest that transformational leadership supports ELO, attention to the team and firm leader profiles should be considered during the recruitment process. This is especially important in service and research firms where leaders are selected more often for their technical than their leadership competencies. Third, to translate individual learning into organizational improvement, firm managers should be aware that the ELO has to be supported by a TL. Indeed, if firms wish to be intelligent, learning and creative, and hope to tackle the intellectual-capital-based new economy, they should foster a climate where they can tap the fullness of human learning potential through a leadership that promotes the charismatic influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

• **Limitations and Directions for Future Research**

As with any research, this study has some limitations that should be considered when interpreting its results. First, this study focuses on a single industry in France: the medical biotechnology. Results should be considered with caution and thus, generalization of the results is to relativize. Therefore, it would be important to test the applicability of the tested model with larger samples and in other contexts. A second limitation is the use of single informants as the source of information in the survey. Thus, there is a possibility of existence of the subjectivity bias. "Although the use of single informants remains the primary research design in most studies, multiple informants would enhance the validity of the research findings" (Jimenez-Jimenez and Sanz-Valle, 2011, p. 416). Third, we have not taken into account contextual factors that may affect the tested model. Other variables, such as the firm size, age, life cycle, environmental turbulence and, intensity of R & D, may be added to the model and yield further insights into our findings.

Some additional recommendations for future research are proposed. One is to consider OL as a process animated by the dynamic of stocks and flows as suggested by Vera and Cross an (2004). Another suggestion is to take into account the precise role played by the strategic leadership with regard to the exploitation and exploration learning processes. According to the literature, exploitation and exploration learning activities could require different leadership styles and may influence differently the innovation performance. Finally, as organizational learning requires some time to affect innovation performance, it may be worthwhile to study our model through longitudinal study.

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